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Pesticide Handling Practices by Farming Households in Relation to Disease Burden: A Case of Migori County, Kenya

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Abstract

Unsafe exposure to pesticides has become an issue of concern globally for the last two decades due to their ecological effect. Data available from Public Health office in Migori County, Kenya over a period of five years from 2011 to 2016 showed increasing disease burden in the population suspected to be as a result of unsafe use of pesticides as well as weak policy interventions. The study was necessitated by human health concern and ecological risks due to handling of pesticides. The objective was to evaluate pesticide handling practices in relation to symptoms of ill-health. Preliminary information was obtained on common ill-health symptoms associated with pesticides (such as eye, skin, stomach, respiratory irritation and mental problems) from literature review and public health officers. Questionnaires and observation schedules were administered to farmers relating to current practices on application and disposal of pesticides in 2016. A sample of 384 farming household heads within a population of 7,500 farming households was identified by stratified purposive sampling based on sub-counties and wards. Triangulation by use of Focus Group Discussions were used and content analysed. The research design was descriptive survey and data analysed by descriptive statistics. Hypothesis testing was done using χ^2 at 0.05 level of confidence. From the sample, 97% of the farmers used pesticides in 2016 and those affected by eye irritation were 33%, skin irritation 29% and 24% by respiratory irritation, stomach irritation 12.5% and mental problems 7.5% ($p(\chi^2 \geq 530.593, df 126) = 0.000$ at $\alpha 0.05$). The farmers (79.5%) showed unsafe handling practices before application of pesticides. The study recommended introduction of affordable and more comfortable protective clothing for farmers and up scaling of extension services on choice, use, storage and disposal of pesticides as vital for ecological sustainability.

Key words: Disease Burden, Ecological Risk, Ill health Symptoms, Pesticides

INTRODUCTION

By 2050, the world's population is projected to reach 9 billion, 34 percent higher than today. Nearly all of this increase will occur in developing countries (FAO, 2015a; IFPRI, 2015). Demands on food have become higher calling for increase in food production to cater for this demand. In third world countries, about 2.3 to 2.6 billion people are supported by agricultural systems (FAO, 2008). Hunger, malnutrition, and poverty remain stubbornly persistent in many developing countries despite advances made in agricultural productivity in recent years. The population of those that are hunger stricken stands at over 350 million in sub-Saharan Africa (FAO, 2015b).

Increased production of agricultural products has resulted to the problem of heavy use of pesticides that interfere with the fragile ecosystem especially in developing countries. A report from World Health Organization indicates that over 200,000 people are killed every year due to toxicity of the dangerous chemicals in pesticides (FAO,2010). Exposure to pesticides leads to several health problems such as asthma, skin rashes, chronic disorders such as emphysema and cancer (Stoytchera, 2011).The strategies for sustainable agriculture call for techno-economic position as well as agro-ecological-ruralist position (Koochafkan *et al.*, 2012). Techno-economic position includes land sparing while agro-ecological-ruralist position involves wildlife-friendly farming opportunities that offer complementary benefits for biodiversity conservation. Organic farmers and agro-ecologists continue to develop and demonstrate models of sustainable agriculture in many countries (FAO, 2010). Pollock *et al.* (2008) realized that sustainable agriculture involves technological approaches to improve sustainability in terms of optimizing inputs and management and in terms of mitigating adverse impacts including those of climate change.

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Bio-monitoring of pesticide levels in bio-specimen has been considered to be an alternative approach to estimating levels of pesticide exposure. Bio-monitoring is the study of the presence and concentration of chemicals in humans where detection of the compound implies that the pesticide is bioavailable and that a section of the critical tissues may have been affected (Schwartz *et al.*, 2015). Bio-monitoring is done through samples of urine, breast milk and red blood cells being tested for pesticide residues. Pesticide self-poisoning is a major public health concern since it accounts for at least one in every seven suicide cases globally (Emma *et al.*, 2017). The number could even be higher since the computation is only made on available data yet there are several regions where data is not available (Page *et al.*, 2017). However, due to variations in exposure, duration and magnitude, routes of absorption and variations in physiology of individuals bio-monitoring of pesticides in tissues has not been very effective (Ye *et al.*, 2013).

In Kenya, some empirical studies have linked pesticide use to farmers' health where increased cases of prevalence of chest pains, running nose, wheezing, difficulties in breathing and throat irritation among farm workers exposed to use of pesticides were reported (Asfaw, 2008). Other respiratory symptoms noted were coughing, chest tightness, dyspnea and dryness of nose (Zuskin *et al.*, 2008). Symptomatic ailments such as headache, sneezing, dizziness, blurred vision and skin irritation were reported to be on the increase between 2005 and 2008 due to increased use of pesticides (Macharia *et al.*, 2013). Pediatric reports indicate a close link between pesticides with birth and foetal defects such as premature birth, low birth weight and congenital abnormality (Schwartz *et al.*, 2015). Environmental exposure to low levels of environmental contaminants also undermines the ability to reproduce by lowering the level of testosterone due to high levels of urinary metabolites such as chlorpyrifos, cabaryl and naphthalene.

The misuse of pesticides has been associated with health problems and environmental contamination worldwide (Remor *et al.*, 2009). Measurement of disease burden is a scientific means of quantifying the comparative magnitude of health loss due to diseases, injury and risk factors by age, sex and geographies for specific points in time (Global Burden of Disease, 2013). Disease burden is measured in terms of Disability Adjusted Life Years (DALY) i.e.

$$PAF = \frac{P(RR-1)}{P(RR-1) + 1}$$

$$P(RR-1) + 1$$

Where PAF= Population Attributable Fraction

RR= Relative Risk

P= Prevalence of exposure (Adopted from Annette *et al.*, 2011)

Figure 1 shows the computed trend of Disease Burden in Migori County from 2011 to 2016 based on available data. The use of pesticides, though necessary in agricultural settings, poses great health risks to farmers, farm workers and their families. Pesticides are among the most extensively used industrial chemicals in the world and are among the most hazardous compounds to human health (Tsimbiri *et al.*, 2015). A combination of several pesticides often increases environmental pollution leading to a heavy disease burden (measured by number of reported cases against the population) which then becomes a determinant of the levels of environmental effect (Chaturvedi *et al.*, 2013).

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Descriptive survey design was used to investigate the pesticide handling practices by farmers before, during and after application. Stratified purposive sampling of crop farmers was used to arrive at a sample of 384 farmers from a population of 7500 farming households based on sub-county, ward and agro-ecological zone. (Yamane, 1967). Yamane' formula method was used.

Formula is $n = \frac{z^2(p)(q)}{d^2}$

$$d^2$$

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where n= sample size

z= standard normal deviate set at 1.96 and corresponding to 95% confidence level ± 5

p= proportion of the population with the desired attribute q= 1.0- p

d= desired precision level allowed ± 5

$$n = (1.96)^2(0.5)(0.5)$$

$$(0.05)^2$$

$$= 384$$

Questionnaires for farmers comprised two sections namely section A, on demographic information and section B on knowledge on how pesticides were used, their handling practices and perception. The items used were open-ended with some closed demanding that respondents tick appropriate responses. Focus group discussions (FGD) were also used. Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) was used to analyse the data collected while FGD were analysed by content. Descriptive statistics such as frequencies, means, standard deviations and percentages were used. Chi square was used for hypothesis testing was done at 0.05 confidence level.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Farmers make decisions with regard to the pesticides that they use. A study in India on pesticides showed that farmers perceived the pesticides to be the most effective means to pest and disease control (Shetty *et al.*, 2010). When a large proportion of farmers use particular pesticides then more of that pesticide is likely to be found in the ecosystem. The direct consequences of increased pesticide contamination to the matrices of soil, water and air, in turn affect the environment and human health. (Achudume *et al.*, 2008).

An item in the study sought to determine the proportion of farmers in Migori County who had used some selected pesticides in the previous year which was 2016. The pesticides selected for study were those that were identified as fast selling by the agro-vet stockiests which included Confidor, Diazol, Round Up, Ridomil and Calcium Ammonium Nitrate (CAN). The proportion of farmers who had used particular pesticides was cross tabulated with the frequency of ill- health symptoms and subjected to chi-square test to determine statistical significance. The results are as shown in Table I

The findings were that 266 (62%) of the farmers sampled had used Confidor, 30 (7%) had used Diazol, 12 (2%), had used Round up, 50 (11.7%) and 344 (80.2%), had used CAN. Only 4 farmers (less than 1%) had used more than one pesticide. The large proportions suggest that farmers believed in the effectiveness of pesticides with regard to their ability to increase production of their farms (Achudume *et al.*, 2008). Exposure to Confidor was highest in Suna East, with 40% of the respondents in Kakrao ward (where a lot of tobacco and vegetables are grown) indicating that 97.6% had used Confidor in 2016. Kuria West had the least exposure with 12.4% of the respondents having used Confidor. Confidor, being a pesticide, is widely used to control insects in vegetables, fruits and tobacco. It contains Imidaclopid which is toxic to mammals, birds, earthworms and bees. Ridomil was widely used in Kuria West (19.3% of the respondents) and the exposure was heaviest in Mekerero and Masaba wards. These are wards where vegetables are grown in large quantities for supply to urban centers namely Isebania and Mabera and beyond. Ridomil is a common fungicide that is usually toxic to terrestrial vertebrates and invertebrates.

Precautions before handling pesticides

Pesticides pose several risks to humans and the environment due to improper handling. An open-ended question was posed with regard to self-protection in order to determine if the farmers had knowledge on the need to wear protective gear when handling pesticides and if they practiced the same. Figure 2 shows the farmers' responses to wearing protective gear per Sub-county. Knowledge often assists individuals to initiate action. Table II is a quantitative analysis (using frequencies and inferential statistics) of the reasons adduced by farmers for not wearing headgear in relation to disease symptoms. Well educated communities train new generations towards becoming responsible environmental citizens (Pretty & Bharucha, 2015). Further analysis was conducted on the responses of the farmers with regard to the reasons for not wearing

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aprons. Aprons actually protect the skin of the farmer from getting into direct contact with pesticides. This, if done properly is likely to reduce incidences of skin irritation. Table III shows the frequencies obtained from the items in the questionnaire that tested actual reasons for not wearing aprons. During FGD, no farmer mentioned protection of the head as important. The discussions majored on apron, gumboots, nose masks and gloves. The primary reason given by farmers for not wearing aprons was discomfort. This may call for redesigning aprons that may be more comfortable yet affordable to the farmers.

Another protective gear that was explored was the gumboots. Gumboots protect the feet against any sharp objects that may bruise them hence serving as a point of secondary entry of pesticides. Besides, they also protect the skin of the feet from direct exposure to pesticides. Table IV provides an analysis of reasons advanced by farmers for not wearing gumboots.

From the sample of 384 respondents, 10 did not respond to the question on gumboots, probably indicating that they did not consider it worthy to protect the feet. A total of 219 out of the 374 respondents indicated that at times they do not wear gumboots due to discomfort. This translates to 58.6% of the respondents with only 8.8% seeing no need for it. The highest frequency of those who thought it was not necessary was from Nyatike. Despite significant differences in terms of wearing protective clothing per sub-county, there was no clear pattern attributable to any individual sub-county. From FGD, it emerged that farmers were generally aware of the dangers of pesticides to humans and recommended wearing of protective clothing as well as washing of the clothing with soap and bathing. However, in actual practice they did not seem to wear the protection. Even washing of the clothes and bathing was done in the streams, hence posing a risk of contaminating the water sources. Some disconnect therefore existed between knowledge and practice. Due to diverse routes through which pesticides enter the body, it called for consideration for a wide range of pre-application measures. The study sought to establish some of the measures that farmers put in place. The findings are shown in Figure 3

Most farmers considered wearing of protective clothing and/or reading of instructions as being the most critical. It was also noted that about 10 farmers did not respond to that item. However, mixing of pesticide in sprayer was given very little consideration across all sub-counties. In Kuria West sub-county, no respondent indicated that the sprayer should be washed with soap. This raised very high possibility of having various concoctions of pesticide in the sprayer due to limited hygiene. Safety and sustainable use of pesticides demand that farmers practice multiple measures in handling the same before use. Less than 1.4% of the respondents per sub-county practiced safety. The major risk of pesticide contamination seemed to stem from improper handling before application.

Precautions after handling of pesticides

A range of practices for safe handling as well as unsafe handling of pesticides were included in the questionnaire and farmers were expected to indicate the ones that they carried out. The practices included 'washing hands and clothes with soap', 'cleaning the sprayer with soap', 'storage of remaining chemical in cupboard', 'showing family members how to mix pesticide and apply' as well as an open-ended item for others where they were expected to specify. The responses were analyzed qualitatively based on available facts and broadly grouped into two, namely risky or safe.

Generally, most farmers practiced safe handling of pesticides after application. This was probably due to the fact that they believed the pesticides were very harmful. The major risk noted during FGD was that farmers recommended burying of pesticide containers after use. That practice has chances of polluting the soil in which they are buried hence interfering with soil microorganisms. Sometimes the same containers may also be washed away to the water sources by surface run off during heavy rains. From the inferential statistics conducted on various pesticide handling practices after use, it was observed that some pattern existed with regard to use of selected pesticides for attainment of sustainable agriculture ($P(\chi^2 \geq 46.249, df 20) = 0.001$ at $\alpha 0.05, N= 384$). The alternative hypothesis that there is a statistically significant relationship between patterns of pesticide handling practices and attainment of sustainable agriculture was therefore accepted.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The study noted that 52.7% of the respondents had multiple reasons for applying pesticides, among them to increase soil fertility, improve yield, pest and disease control as well as weed control ($p(\chi^2 \geq 136.066, df$

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44) = 0.000 at α 0.05). Among the farmers 56.2% relied on their own experience to decide on the type of pesticide, quantity to apply and when to apply it. Only 22.4% of the respondents consulted the extension officers. Also, 82.5% of the respondents mixed the pesticides in other containers such as pots and water buckets, as opposed to use of knapsack sprayer. Agitation or stirring of the pesticides was done by use of sticks or kitchen cutlery by 92.8%. The only protection against abuse of pesticides that was known by the most farmers was wearing protective clothing.

This study concluded that farmers in Migori County needed training and proper policy on handling and use of pesticides in order to mitigate against the ecological risk and protect themselves against ill-health symptoms attributable to these pesticides. This could be achieved through proper empowerment of Agricultural Extension Service Providers (AESP) with requisite knowledge on sustainable agriculture. The study recommended uniform and well-structured training of the AESP on how the pesticides can be used for sustainable agriculture in Migori County. The study also recommends further research on why some farmers did not respond to the question on why they did not wear protective gear.

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Table I: Proportion of farmers in Migori County who had used pesticides in 2016 and significance level in relation to ill-health.

Pesticide	Farmers who used pesticide (n)	Percentage of sample	χ^2	df	P
Confidor	266	62	45.962	4	0.000
Diazol	30	7	9.998	4	0.040
Round Up	12	2	10.560	4	0.030
Ridomil	50	11.7	4.668	4	0.323
CAN	344	80.2	30.108	4	0.000

 α 0.05

*Not used pesticide 40 respondents

Table II: Reasons why farmers do not wear headgear per sub-county.

Sub-county	Discomfort	Unaffordable	No need for it	Total
Suna East	8	15	47	70
Suna West	14	31	27	72
Uriri	4	24	24	52
Nyatike	11	41	28	80
Kuria West	16	18	22	56
Total	53	129	148	330

P ($\chi^2 \geq 41.979$, df 24) = 0.013 at α 0.05 N= 330

*Non response 44

Table III: Reasons why farmers do not wear apron per sub-county.

Sub-county	Discomfort	Unaffordable	No need for it	Total
Suna East	58	13	1	72
Suna West	38	25	10	73
Uriri	29	18	6	53
Nyatike	48	35	9	93
Kuria West	46	34	2	82
Total	219	125	28	373

P ($\chi^2 \geq 77.439$, df 44) = 0.001 at α 0.05 N= 373

*Non response 11

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Table IV: Reasons why farmers do not wear gumboots per sub-county.

Sub-county	Discomfort	Unaffordable	No need for it	Total
Suna East	36	31	3	70
Suna West	46	23	8	77
Uriri	26	23	5	54
Nyatike	42	32	13	87
Kuria West	69	13	4	86
Total	219	122	33	374

$P(\chi^2 \geq 108.697, df 40) = 0.000$ at $\alpha 0.05$ N= 374

*Non response 10

Figure 1: Migori County disease burden trend in relation to agrochemicals
(Source, Migori County Public Health Office, 2016)

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Figure 2: Knowledge on need for protective clothing

$P(\chi^2 \geq 39.164, df 4) = 0.000$ at $\alpha 0.05$ N= 384

Figure 3: Precautionary measures before applying pesticides

$P(\chi^2 \geq 64.673, df 20) = 0.000$ at $\alpha 0.05$ N= 384